

INNOVATIVE IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN VEGETABLE AND COTTON GROWING

Abdrashitova E.V.

Department of Biology at Chirchik State Pedagogical University in Chirchik, Uzbekistan

Abstract. *The article discusses the new agrarian policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan and new approaches to financing the development of agro-industrial complex. Timely state reforms and strategic planning in the field of attracting investments in the agrarian sector of the Republic.*

Keywords: *Greenhouse, vegetable products, agro-industrial complex, agri-food market, drip irrigation, market-based mechanisms, investment process, monitoring.*

Introduction. New technologies are capturing more and more industries that can increase the productivity of agricultural enterprises. Innovative technologies in agriculture are modern agricultural machinery, computers, drones, mobile devices, robotics, and modern, more advanced software. Artificial intelligence can operate with a large amount of data, perform analysis, and make recommendations. It is this approach and the use of innovative technologies that make it possible to obtain high crop yields without polluting the soil, air, and water, without depleting natural resources, and without affecting the ecosystem and biodiversity. Technologies in agriculture are improving. It is necessary to keep pace with progress, use advanced technologies, and introduce modern equipment, this provides an opportunity for growth. New technologies make it possible to apply only those fertilizers that are required in a given area, to select an irrigation system, and the necessary tillage for a given crop. From the introduction of modern farming methods, all participants in the agro-industrial chain save time and resources, most of the profit, and costs, reduce the impact on water bodies, and soil, increase productivity without reducing labor costs, predict potential problems, eliminate in time, helps agricultural producers more accurately make a budget forecast for the new season. Agricultural productivity 10 years ago in Uzbekistan was falling lower and lower, decisions had to be made urgently. The Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has set a task for agriculture to increase the production and quality of vegetables, and make them available to the population throughout the year^{7,10}.

Material and methods. This is one of the main priorities. Consumption of vegetables every day is one of the main economic indicators of the well-being and health of the nation. Consumption of vitamins in natural form is required all year round. An average person needs around 130-150 kg of vegetables per year¹. Because Uzbekistan is located in a zone of sharply continental climate conditions do not allow growing vegetables in open ground throughout the year. The cultivation of vegetable products is seasonal, and 25% of their total quantity should be grown in greenhouses, greenhouses, and insulated soil⁹. In this regard, it is necessary to develop some areas of the agricultural sector. Develop greenhouse farming at an accelerated pace and introduce advanced technologies. Learn from China, Israel, Spain, and Holland, where greenhouse farming has been successfully developing for a long time and, accordingly, has developed the most advanced technologies and production capacities and invaluable experience. To implement the plans outlined by the president and the government, large investments will be required in the agricultural sector^{7,8,9,10}.

Results. Our main weaknesses are vegetable growing and horticulture, modernization of agricultural machinery and equipment, development of rural areas and agricultural science, breeding, genetics, and bio-additives^{4,7}. Agriculture has become a high-tech business. Businesses

want to know what transformations are planned in various sectors and divisions of agriculture and what changes are planned in crop production, how the use of digital technologies helps to increase production volumes and reduce their costs. The investor seeks to calculate in advance all the risks associated with an unpredictable business¹. Enterprises that use new technologies for innovative growth now, will receive reliable and guaranteed results in the agricultural market shortly⁴. The agri-food complex of Uzbekistan has received a new direction in development, it has a great future. The country is rich in land resources that await development, and human and natural potential. Today in Uzbekistan there are about 6.5 thousand hectares of greenhouses, of which 1.1 thousand hectares (17%) are hydroponic and 4.9 thousand hectares (83%) are greenhouses with soil cultivation method⁴. The interest of large capital in greenhouse farming is increasing. The total volume of investments attracted into the development of the republic's agricultural complex during the period from the beginning of the project implementation in agriculture amounted to 15.5 trillion. sums and the share in the total volume of investments in fixed assets for all types of economic activity in the republic were noted at 8.2%^{5,12}. Thanks to government support and investments in greenhouse farming, the region has strengthened production capacity and ensured good growth in vegetables and fruits. Along with milk and meat, mushrooms, protected soil vegetables, fish, and poultry are grown. In 2021, 271 thousand tons of products were produced in greenhouses in Uzbekistan, of which 167 thousand tons were tomatoes, that is, 62% of the total volume of greenhouse products. In 2022, it is planned to produce 342 thousand tons of products in greenhouses, of which 199 thousand tons are tomatoes, which is, 58% of the total production of greenhouse products¹⁰. Consequently, in 2022, the volume of production of greenhouse products in Uzbekistan is planned to increase by 26% compared to last year, and greenhouse tomatoes - by 19%. The main part of products grown in greenhouses in the Bukhara, Khorezm, Samarkand, and Tashkent regions of the country are tomatoes, bell peppers, cucumbers, eggplants and greens¹⁰. Greenhouse farms in Uzbekistan use modern technologies for growing vegetables from countries such as China, Germany, Turkey, and Israel. To reduce the consumption of fertilizers and irrigation water, drip irrigation is used in greenhouses, and remote control is carried out by artificial intelligence. As a result, the crop grown in such a greenhouse increases by 30% compared to the traditional method, and the amount of water and fertilizer consumed is reduced by 30-40%. In the context of the use of innovative technologies, state support is necessary, especially for small and medium-sized businesses, and start-up entrepreneurs. Currently, the Ministry of Agriculture is trying various financing methods to make subsidized loan accessible to small farms. For large agricultural enterprises that are engaged in growing agricultural products, processing them, selling them, conducting trade and purchasing activities, and purchasing surplus agricultural products from the population, it is not profitable to get a subsidized, short-term loan, they need “long-term money”⁶ long-term loans. The Republic faces the difficult and long-term task of providing agricultural producers with finance, high-quality seed material, mineral fertilizers, equipment, and fuel, which will allow farms to work without downtime or haste, according to a plan. When receiving loans, the mechanism must be transparent and worked out to the smallest detail. Many auxiliary sectors in agricultural production need to be developed or need to be formed from scratch. The most important areas are domestic selection, genetics, and the production of high-quality seed and planting material. This is a strategic issue, our food security and independence. This is the health and economic well-being of the nation. The state supports and develops family enterprises, small farmers and entrepreneurs, and dekhkan farms. By 2030, there will be 28 thousand 700 farms in Uzbekistan⁵. Moreover, in Uzbekistan, the rural population is 60%. The Republic is developing

agricultural cooperation and creating conditions for income growth for residents of rural areas. Improves the quality of life in rural areas. Develops the infrastructure and social sphere of the village⁷. We are talking about the development of modern medical institutions with broad and narrow specialists, the construction and equipping of modern rural schools, kindergartens, sports schools, and other public institutions with new equipment and specialists². It gasifies remote villages improves the quality of drinking water provides public sewerage, and provides high-quality mobile communications and the Internet to remote settlements: everything is important for a rural resident. Thereby bringing rural areas closer to the city and merging them into the general social and economic space of the country. But the most important thing is to update the condition of local roads^{3,4,5}. To make rural life more modern, comfortable, and attractive. Constantly improve everyday life so that all people and each person feel the changes and care of the state. Only by creating conditions for improving the quality of life and self-realization will the Republic ensure sustainable development of the village. We must remember that the most important thing is people and territories. The President and the government understand this and are actively developing new sets of laws and using financing mechanisms in the construction of new greenhouse complexes with modern energy-saving technologies. The past year for the greenhouse market was one of the most successful in recent years. 251 hectares of new greenhouses were introduced, and these are fifth-generation complexes where modern energy-saving technologies are used. Thanks to this approach, the average yield in winter greenhouse farms increased to a record level of 60 kg/sq. m. The Ministry of Agriculture claims that the average yield has increased by 33%⁴. Consequently, serious changes are also expected in the field of land relations in the coming years. The first step towards reforming the rights to use agricultural land was already taken in September 2020 by introducing a sublease mechanism to grow agricultural products, which will allow the most efficient use of valuable land resources¹⁰. Between 2017 and 2022, reforms were carried out in the agriculture of Uzbekistan, the results of which made it possible to ensure sustainable growth of the industry and increase resource conservation. In the future, they will help to fully utilize the existing potential of the republic in agricultural development and bring Uzbekistan to the first position in the production and export of agri-food products¹¹.

For the Republic, cotton growing is the main economically profitable agricultural crop. Great production and scientific potential have been accumulated in cotton growing. Growing cotton even on poor soils brings decent income. However, the yield of cotton crops depends on the climate of the region and the type of cotton. From 1 hectare of area, you can get from 80 to 120 centners of fiber with natural irrigation. Another advantage of cotton growing is that there are few farms involved in growing the crop, and the demand for raw materials on the market is very high.

In the countries of Central Asia, cotton has always been grown using irrigation. In Uzbekistan, about 4.5 million hectares are allocated for cotton on irrigated land, compared to drip irrigation with 400 thousand hectares. This technology is gaining momentum. Cotton is a delicate crop, sensitive to low temperatures. Spring frosts destroy the seedlings, and large areas have to be reseeded. Under favorable conditions, seedlings appear in the fields 5-6 days earlier. For medium-fiber cotton varieties, the growing season is 125–150 days, and for fine-fiber cotton from 145–160 days. To grow a good harvest, you need up to 210-220 days without frost, the temperature is +25°C, during the flowering of the plant the temperature should be +26–30°C. During flowering and boll formation, cotton plants consume more water. Modern methods of growing cotton make it possible to overcome these difficulties; they use several methods of irrigating cotton - gravity,

rain, and drip¹³. Each of these methods has both positive aspects and disadvantages. Gravity irrigation is carried out through furrows, channels, reinforced concrete trays, or underground pipelines. The irrigation method is expensive, water consumption is high, and uniform watering of the field is not ensured. Rainfall installations are used for overhead irrigation of cotton. Water is supplied into the air and, in a finely dispersed form, reaches plants and soil. The method is quite simple, it moisturizes the soil and plants well. Disadvantages: high water consumption, and difficult in complying with irrigation standards¹³. If you use drip irrigation technology for cotton, you need a whole complex of special equipment: a system of pipes, filtration equipment, for applying fertilizers, pipelines, and other components. When drip irrigation, the distance between the rows of plants should be from 50 to 100 centimeters, depending on the crop variety, the distance between the droppers should be from 30 to 75 centimeters. Drip lines are laid in rows; each plant has its dropper with water. Such an irrigation system regulates the water supply - its speed, and intensity and precisely controls the watering rate. Through the water supply system, you can fertilize throughout the entire growing season, and add fertilizers, and stimulants for plant growth and development. Drip lines can be laid on the soil surface or with a recess for direct root irrigation¹³. Drip irrigation of cotton and vegetable crops is more economically efficient and less risky. This irrigation method allows you to obtain a higher yield by 15-20% while saving water and energy resources and using them more efficiently. Drip irrigation allows you to meet the daily water needs of the plant, protects against water stress, and promotes the smooth development and growth of the crop. Drip irrigation creates better conditions for crop development and improves the quality of the resulting fiber, oil, and other raw cotton products. Water is supplied to each plant at a rationed rate. This method is especially effective in arid regions where the amount of water is limited, and poor soils, fertilizing, and mineral fertilizers can be supplied in doses. Fertilizers are applied only to the crop, increasing the efficiency of feeding. For example, at the beginning of flowering, the plant's need not only for more water, but also for nutrients increases and continues until the boxes open. During this period, the plant is fed throughout the entire growing season.

Conclusion. This technology reduces the absorption of nitrates by the plant, which helps preserve the seed pods on the cotton bush. The amount of water must be calculated accurately since its deficiency or excess has a bad effect on the balance of growth of the seed parts of the plant and leaves¹³. Developing technology, choosing the right variety, and installing highly efficient irrigation systems will make growing cotton and vegetables profitable and environmentally friendly. Uzbekistan, together with the countries of the Central Asian region, is forming a new type of agri-food market. Modern approaches to solving the food problem provide conditions for stable, effective, rational reproduction and functioning of the agricultural sector.

Consequently, using innovative technologies, is a movement towards productive and sustainable development of agriculture, which will ensure food security in the face of the growing needs of the population and the economic prosperity of the country.

REFERENCES

1. Alpamisova G.B, Abdrashitova E.V. (2023) Znachenie parnikov v vyrashchivanii ekologicheski chistoj produkcii i obespechenie prodovol'stvennoj bezopasnosti. Trudy mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-prakticheskoy konferencii <<AUEZOVSKIE CHTENIYA – 21: NOVYJ KAZAHSTAN – BUDUSHCHEE STRANY>> Shymkent: YUKU im. M. Auezova.
2. Abdrashitova E.V., Allanozarova I.A. “Analiz perspektiv, problem i putej ih resheniya v metodike prepodavaniya biologii v shkole” [“Analysis of prospects, problems and ways to

- solve them in the methodology of teaching biology at school.”] Bulletin of N U Uz. Tashkent-2022. 69-71 p.
3. Bulletin of the agro-industrial complex 05 (2018) Farmers.
 4. Economic Review No. 5 (233) 2019; № 2 (266) 2022; № 11/2022
 5. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 04/17/2018 No. PP-3671 “On measures to organize the activities of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.”
 6. Ilyina D. “Liberalizatsiya eksporta i rasshirenie podderzhki eksporterov plodoovoshchnoj produkcii v 2017-2021g.” [“Liberalization of exports and expansion of support for exporters of fruits and vegetables in 2017-2021.”] Journal "Economics: analyzes and forecasts No. 1 (12) January-March 2021 p. 78-81
 7. FAO. Analytical report “The State of Food and Agriculture: Investing in agriculture for a better future” Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Rome, 2012.
 8. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 29, 2020 No. ZRU-639 “On introducing amendments and additions to certain legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to increase the efficiency of use of agricultural lands and forestry.”
 9. Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan November 04, 2022
 10. <https://www.neo-agriservis.ru>